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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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AN ASSESSMENT OF THE INADEQUACIES OF PERSONNEL TOWARDS CURBING COMMERCIAL MALPRACTICES IN MARKETS IN NIGERIA: HISBAH INSTITUTION AS AN OPTION

By

Ismail Danjuma Yusuf,* Fatima Tanimu Bindawa**

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ABSTRACT

This paper studies the institution of hisbah which simply ensures that illegalities as well as indecencies are abhorred while encouraging and upholding the virtues and values enshrined in Islamic law. Indeed, hisbah as an institution is traceable to the Prophetic era and the subsequent era thereby conferring it a lawful status in Islamic law. No doubt, many medieval and contemporary legal systems have tried to adopt the institution of hisbah. In the northern states of Nigeria, for example, Governors via various laws have introduced hisbah to serve certain religious purposes which include but not limited to ensuring fair dealings in interpersonal relationships. Nigerian markets are characterized with a number of economic malpractices which include price hike, hoarding and artificial scarcity of goods and services, and this undoubtedly promotes hardship on all and sundry. The paper finds that governmental efforts which include promulgation of the Price Control Act (1977), establishment of Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission and other similar efforts across all tiers of government appear not only inadequate but also ineffective in managing economic malpractices in the country. The paper adopts doctrinal method and this helps in studying economic malpractices of Nigerian markets and marketers, and the breakthroughs recorded by hisbah in managing economic malpractices in Nigeria especially in the states with hisbah framework. This paper, therefore, suggests hisbah as an effective panacea towards curbing these unnecessary economic excesses and saboteurs by complementing the existing governmental gaits.

Keywords: Hisbah, Nigerian Markets, Marketers, Economic Malpractices

1. INTRODUCTION

In maintaining social order, the need to have enforcement agencies or bodies is very imperative. This is because enforceability of executive and legislative orders is one of the core businesses of every promising government. Otherwise, these orders become mere cosmetic provisions and apparently, social injustice and disorder become the order of the day¹.

The institution of hisbah occupies a fundamental and foundational status in a decent and proper Islamic state. This institution is a striking feature of Islamic governance. Where this institution is missing, proper Islamic governance becomes a mirage. Islam as a perfect religion and total way of life makes provision for everything, governance inclusive. The sophisticated nature of Islamic law accounts for its success and relevance throughout ages in all spheres of human endeavors².

The provision of Islamic law touches all facets of human endeavours, economic life inclusive. Indeed, the application of Islamic law is all encompassing, not restrictive making the full application imperative for Muslims. The Qur'an reads:

O you believers! Enter the fold of Islam completely and follow not the footsteps of Shaytan for he is a well-known enemy (to you)³

It follows, therefore, that acts of worship (Ibadat) and Interpersonal relationship (*Mu'amalat*) are largely and completely regulated by Islamic law. Economic life through many ways including commercial transactions form the fulcrum of the mechanism that brings human interaction to limelight. Islam forbids laziness and idleness, Muslims by default are expected to engage in every legal and lawful means of earning livelihood⁴.

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¹<https://www.realclearpolitics.com/articles/2018/11/01/when_laws_are_not_enforced_anarchy_follows_138514.html#> accessed 20 July 2023

² Black, A., Esmaeili, H. & Hosen, N. (2013). Modern perspectives on Islamic Law. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited. pp.2-4

³ Al-Baqarah v 206

⁴ See Baqarah v 167 and Jumu'ah v 10

In ensuring compliance to the extant provisions of Islamic law, hisbah exists to ensure that Muslims comply with the legal injunctions by encouraging and promoting what is good, and discouraging people from perpetrating in obscure and bad actions. Similarly, hisbah is concerned with the responsibility of protecting rights as it affects Allah and human beings.

In Nigeria, markets⁵ are characterized with a number of economic malpractices negative features unjustly consuming prospective consumers of their hard-earned scarce resources with or without enjoying the deserved goods and services paid for. It is palpable to note that while approaching the festive periods in Nigeria,⁶ the sporadic scarcity of goods and services as well as the exorbitant nature of market prices are difficult to explain owing to unchecked hoarding and other economic improprieties. Admittedly, government through agencies and legislations⁷ has taken proactive steps to address these illegal activities but all proved futile.

This paper, therefore, gives the techno-legal and conceptual meanings of *hisbah* as well as the legal basis of *hisbah* in Islamic law. In addition, it discusses the concept of economic malpractices as operative in Nigeria and proposes hisbah as an effective and efficient mechanism of curbing the exploitative tendency cum economic malpractices of Nigerian marketers and markets.

1.1 Statement of Problem

Economic sabotage and malpractices have saturated Nigerian markets and this explains why tremendous efforts have been commissioned in arresting these malpractices. These efforts include but not limited to the promulgation of some laws (e.g. Price Control Act of 1977) and establishment of some agencies (e.g. Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission). These laws and agencies appear redundant and cosmetic because economic malpractices persist. The introduction of Hisbah in a number of northern states of Nigeria has no doubt helped in preventing a number of socio-economic crimes. Unless and until the hisbah approach in managing

⁵ Markets for the purpose of this paper include persons and authorities rendering various goods and services.

⁶ During Ramdan for example, there is hoarding of staple foods and prices of these commodities are skyrocketed.

⁷ For example, the proclamation of the Price Control Act of 1977 and establishment of Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission in 2008

economic malpractices is added to the tremendous efforts made by the Nigerian government, management of economic malpractices may be a mirage.

2. THE CONCEPTUAL MEANING OF *HISBAH* IN ISLAMIC LAW

Literarily, the term *hisbah* is rooted from the word '*hasaba*' which can simply be translated to mean to 'calculate', 'determine', 'account', 'measure'⁸ among other synonymous meanings. Its verbal form entails being anticipatory of a divine reward for a meritorious act. This in Arabic parlance is technically referred to as '*ihtasabah*'. Technically, *hisbah* means enjoining what is good when its neglect becomes obvious and forbidding what is improper when its commission becomes apparent in the community⁹. Also, it is a body created by Islamic law to monitor the conduct of citizens. Simply put, this body is set up to ensure maximum compliance with the almost neglected guidelines and principles of Islamic law.

Fodiy¹⁰ asserts that for a successful and better society, a decent, complete and sophisticated institution of *hisbah* that will enjoin good and forbid bad must be put in place. According to him, with *hisbah* in place, the tendency is high that one would attain success in this world and hereafter. *Hisbah* according to him implements what is proper and prevents what is improper.

The institution of *hisbah* is predicated on four fundamental cardinal principles. The first being the *muhtasib* (one who prevents sin or enjoins good), *muhtasb alayhi* (one whose actions of *muhtasib* are directed to), *muhtasib fihi* (the actual sin which is prevented or the good that is being encouraged) and *nafs al-ihtisāb* (the way of preventing sins or enjoining good)¹¹. For a person to be a *muhtasib*¹², certain laid down conditions must be satisfied. An officer of *hisbah* must be:

1. Legally competent and free from any legal impediment.

⁸ Al-Ma'any Arabic-English Dictionary <https://www.almaany.com/en/dict/ar-en/%D8%AD%D8%B3%D8%A8%D8%A9/#google_vignette> accessed 22 June 2024

⁹Abi Ya'la Muhammed bin Hussayn Al-Farra Al-Hanbali '*Al-Ahkām Al-Sultaniyyah*' (2006): Lebanon- Darul – Kotob Al-Ilmiyyah p.325

¹⁰A. Fodiy o '*Guide to Hisbah*' (2001) Kaduna: Iqra Publishers p.18

¹¹ Abu Hamid Al-Gazali *Ihyāu Ulumu Ad-Dīn* v ol. II (2011) Lebanon: Dar Al-Kotob Al-Ilmiyyah p.533

¹²An officer of *hisbah*

2. In addition to this, he must be an upright and capable fellow who is saddled with the responsibility of preventing people from committing both major and minor sins¹³.

Hisbah concerns itself with enjoining what is good and forbidding what is bad. This may apparently affect the rights of Allah, the rights of man or having both rights overlapped. *Al-Muhtasib* must be a Muslim, an adult who is free from any legal impediment. Furthermore, a person whose words would not be welcomed by the society should not be a *Muhtasib*. In other words, a person whose words would not be accepted by the people cannot enjoin good and forbid bad but can join in the execution of any of the duties of a *Muhtasib*. It should be noted that the permission of *Imam* is not needed to be a *Muhtasib* nor one is needed to be appointed before one can be a *Muhtasib* since the duties of a *Muhtasib* are equally shouldered on every legally competent Muslim. It is a serious misconception that only certain categories of persons can be officers of *hisbah*. *Hisbah* can be done by a son to his father and vice-versa, student to his teacher and in the opposite direction, as slave to his master and otherwise and so on¹⁴. In any event, while undertaking a duty as a *Muhtasib*, one should be mild and gentle in his approach. The second pillar of *hisbah* is the subject of *hisbah* i.e. the actual act that needs the attention of a *Muhtasib*. Such act must be *harām* and such act of *Muhtasib* should not be done as a result of spying, known evil is to be addressed. The third pillar of *hisbah* is the action of *hisbah*. The act that needs the attention of *hisbah* should not be detected through spying, the person needs to know the definition as evil, then preaching follows in the manner prescribed by the Qur'an and *Sunnah*. Abuse and blame will now follow if no adherence to the preaching is noticed.

3. **SIGNIFICANCE OF HISBAH IN ISLAMIC LAW**

The institution of *hisbah* is no doubt one of the salient features of Islamic affairs and as a result of this, previous governments in Islam attach importance to this institution so much that it is directly under their watch. From the onset, it has been stated that the core objective of the institution of *hisbah* is to encourage/assist people to do good and discourage/prevent people from doing evil. The derivable benefits of this

¹³Abu Hamid Al-Gazali...p.533

¹⁴ Abu Hamid Al-Gazali,...p.583

institution are invaluable for the betterment of mankind and Muslims, particularly. The duties of *hisbah* in Islam are the yearnings of our present society¹⁵. In essence, where the duties of *hisbah* are maximally discharged, the society will go a long way to prosper spiritually, politically and economically. Against this backdrop, it is important to discuss the significance and importance of the institution of *hisbah* in ideal Islamic governance as far as Islam is concerned. It is argued that for an appreciable grasp of the significance of *hisbah*, making recourse to the functions of *hisbah* in Islamic law is certainly indispensable. The functions of *hisbah* as the name suggests include but not limited to the following:

1. *Al amr bil ma'rūf*: this means enjoining what is good. By this, *hisbah* is to ensure that people are encouraged and assisted to do all socially and religiously rewarding activities. By this, man is saved from the inhumane activities of his fellow man.
2. *Annahyu 'anil munkar*: this means forbidding evil. This is another important responsibility of *hisbah*. Just as the first duty, the institution is saddled with the responsibility of discouraging and preventing people from doing bad. If this is successfully done, the society will definitely prosper in no small measure.
3. And such other duties as may be needed to give effect to the first two duties mentioned above.

One cannot therefore imagine the level of sanity and development of a state where an institution successfully performs the aforementioned responsibilities.

4. HISBAH IN NIGERIA

Nigeria by the provision of the Constitution is a secular state¹⁶ which suggests that the Nigerian state is religiously neutral. However, the community reading of section 275 and section 4(7) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended) make it legal for a number of states in Nigeria to set Shari'ah-compliant mechanisms (inclusive of Hisbah) in place. It is on the strength of this that a number of states particularly in the northern Nigeria brought into fruition a formal application

¹⁵A. Zubair 'Introduction to Islamic Constitutional Law and administrative Law' (2018) Kaduna: Da'wah Foresight Services p.342

¹⁶ See section 10 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended)

of Islamic law within the framework of the constitution. States like Zamfara, Kano, Sokoto, Katsina, Niger, Kebbi, Borno, Jigawa, Kaduna and Yobe have a well classed Hisbah in place. In avoiding loquaciousness in this paper, it suffices to make an allusion to a few states with regimented hisbah operation.

In Kano State, Hisbah came into existence as a result of re-introduction of Islamic law in Kano state in the year 2003. The Board is one of the shariah implementation agencies of the state established in the year 2003 under the legislative law No. 4 of 2003 to implement some essential programs in furtherance of implementing Islamic law in Kano state. The principal function of the agency is to enjoin the citizenry to do good and shun bad deeds¹⁷. Kano State Hisbah Board Law 2003, Law No.4 of 2003 sanctions Hisbah in the state to ensure that citizens eschew all bad comportments and embrace good conducts. Section 7(d) of law provides that hisbah is to advise against acquisition of interest, usury, hoarding and speculation in furtherance of arresting all forms of economic malpractices. It is thus in order for hisbah to embark on patrol and surveillance on key areas including markets to resist all forms of illegalities and irregularities¹⁸. It is instructive to note that hisbah in Kano state has official presence in all the 44 local government areas of state and this has helped in making sure the functions of hisbah are well performed throughout the state. Of course, not without some challenges, hisbah has really helped in arresting economic malpractices in the state.

In Zamfara State, section 4(1) of the Zamfara State Hisbah Commission (Establishment) Law 2003¹⁹ establishes in the state the Hisbah Commission. Section 6(6) of the law empowers the commission:

To take every measure to ensure proper conformity to the teachings of Shariah by the general public in matters of worship, dress code and social or **business** interactions and relationships (emphasis ours)

The law further provides:

¹⁷ ID Yusuf 'A Juristic Analysis of the Contemporary Institution of Hisbah: A Case Study of the Kano State Hisbah Board' An LL.M Dissertation Submitted to the Faculty of Law, University of Ilorin (2019)

¹⁸ < <https://kanostatehisbahboard.com.ng/about-us/> >

¹⁹ This law was amended in 2018 (Zamfara State Hisbah Commission (Establishment) Law No.17, 2003) amendment Law, 2018)

The Governor shall on the advice (sic) of the Commission establish Hisbah Committees in each of the Local Government Councils of the State. The Commission shall nominate persons that may be appointed in the Local Government Committees.

5. ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES DEFINED

Economic malpractices embody unethical and illegal commercial activities with the sole aim of having undue advantage over a potential-innocent consumer. These involve negative activities within markets and marketers such as fraud, hoarding, price hike, monopolistic arrangement etc. Undoubtedly, these activities truncate the wellbeing of all and sundry. Indeed, financial losses, market distortion, absence of trust and social disorder are some of the negative consequences of these illegal activities.

In Islam, economic malpractices are not only unethical but forbidden. Islamic economic principles support equity, transparency, fairness and accountability in commercial activities. Islamic economic system is thus concerned with just and equitable economic principles.

6. LEGAL INJUNCTIONS AGAINST ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES

Islam approves of engaging in economic and commercial activities. In fact, Islam encourages involvement in legitimate means of earning. In the Qur'an, Allah Says:

Then when the (Jumu'ah) Salat (prayer) is ended, you may disperse through the land and seek the Bounty of Allah (by working, etc), and that remember Allah much: that you may be successful²⁰

Furthermore, the Prophet was reported to have said:

Nobody has ever eaten a better meal than that which he earned by working with his hand. The Prophet of Allah Dawud used to eat from the earnings of his manual labour²¹

²⁰ Qur'an Chapter 62 verse 10

²¹ Bukhari; 2072

However, despite the allowance given to commercial and economic activities by Islamic law, there are strict divine directives directing and regulating the conduct of economic and commercial activities. At this juncture, it suffices to mention a few of those divine directives. In the Qur'an, Allah says:

Woe to *Al-Mutaffifin* (those who give less measure and weight)

Those who, when they have to receive by measure from men, demand full measure. And when they have to give by measure or weight to (other) men, give less than due. Do they not think that they will be resurrected (for reckoning)²²

In another chapter of the Qur'an, Allah says:

And O my people! Give full measure and weight in justice and reduce not the things that are due to the people, and do not commit mischief in the land, causing corruption²³

Allah also says in the Qur'an

Give full measure, and cause no loss (to others)

And weigh with the true and straight balance

And defraud not people by reducing their things, nor do evil, making corruption and mischief in the land²⁴

Similarly, the Prophet (PBUH) in a number of his sayings proscribed unethical commercial dealings and economic sharp practices. For example, he was quoted to have said:

It is not justified for a Muslim to put for sale a commodity that is inherently defective unless he reveals the defect (leaving the buyer or consumer with the option to conclude the contract or rescind same)²⁵

He also said "*whoever cheats is not of us*"²⁶.

One can discern from the foregoing that Islamic law abhors all manners of economic malpractices.

²² Quran chapter 83 verses 1-4

²³ Quran chapter 11 verse 85

²⁴ Qur'an chapter 26 verses 181-183

²⁵ Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Yazid bin Abdulwahab al-Rabi' al-Qazvini 'Sunan Ibn Majah' (Darul Salam, Riyadh, 2007) Book 12, Hadith 110

²⁶ Imam Abul-Hussain Muslim bin Hajjaj 'Sahih Muslim' (Darul Salam, Riyadh, 2007)

7. GOVERNMENTAL EFFORTS IN MANAGING ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES IN NIGERIA

The government in Nigeria has undoubtedly taken numerous steps to arrest all forms of economic malpractices and this informs the establishment of agencies via their respective Acts²⁷ and in giving a fair discourse, in this paper, recourse shall be made to a few of them. To start with, Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) which is established principally to standardise and regulate the quality of products in Nigeria. It further prepares standards relating to product, measurement, materials, etc.²⁸. Section 5 (1) (b) provides that:

To undertake investigation as necessary into the quality of facilities, materials and products in Nigeria and establish quality assurance system including certification of factories, products and laboratories²⁹

Section 17 of the same Act enables the Director General of the Organisation to confiscate, destroy and prohibit the sale of substandard products. In ensuring economic sanity, the Organisation sealed a building for housing adulterated products of an original product³⁰

Similarly, the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission was established through the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Act (2018). Among other things, it ensures fair dealing in every facet of commercial and economic transaction. Section 17 of the Act generally prohibits anti-competitive agreements, unfair and deceptive marketing and business practices. The Act further provides that consumers' interests receive consideration appropriately and makes available certain redresses to consumers whose interests have been economically shortchanged. In giving effect to the above, section 18 (f) empowers the Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission to seal up any premises or business found wanting of economic or commercial delinquencies. In confirming the potency of this body, the

²⁷ Such as National Agency for Food and Drug Administration and Control (NAFDAC), Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Petroleum Regulatory (NMDPR) etc.

²⁸ <https://nepc.gov.ng/blog/strategic-partner/son/> accessed 21 August 2024

²⁹ S.5 (1) (b) of Standard Organization of Nigeria Act No 14, 2015

³⁰ https://www.vanguardngr.com/2020/12/son-seals-lagos-plaza-a-adulterating-lubricants/#google_vignette accessed 21 August 2024

commission recently sealed a shop for price gouging and other economic indecencies³¹.

Notwithstanding the accomplishments of the Nigerian Government in managing economic malpractices through the array of sophisticated mechanisms put in place, it is observed that dearth of personnel among other challenges make economic malpractices thriving and usual practices.

8. HISBAH AND ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES IN ISLAMIC LAW

One of the messages brought by Islam through the Prophet is the administration of good governance and this was demonstrated by a number of institutions established by the Prophet. *Hisbah* as a name although did not exist during the era of the Prophet but by conduct, he demonstrated the institution by *hisbah* directly and through some of his companions. Suffice to say that a number of episodes have confirmed our assertions.

Once upon a time, on the Authority of Abu Hurairah, the Messenger of Allah (SAW) while taking a walk around the community (during his oversight function) ran into a pile of grains meant for sale. He inserted his hand deeply inside the grains and discovered it was wet. When he questioned the seller, he replied that it got wet as a result of downpour. The Prophet remarked that why didn't he put it on top so that people can see it and then he says:

Whoever deceives is not of us³²

The above explains succinctly the role of the Prophet in making the market free of indecencies which is one of the main services expected from a well arranged *hisbah*.

Also besides initiating actual investigation on his own, he received complaints from public and answered questions with regard to business transactions. Later on, when he was too busy to do many of these responsibilities and the need to appoint agents became imperative and he eventually appointed some of his companions. Sa'id Ibn Al'as Ibn Mu'awiyah was appointed for the Makkan markets, then Abdullahi Ibn Usaibah Ibn Al'as and Umar Ibn Khattab were both assigned to the market of Medina

³¹ <https://dailytrust.com/photos-fccpc-seals-off-abuja-store-over-price-fixing/>

³² Sahih Bukhari 6659 available on <https://abuaminaelias.com/dailyhadithonline/2012/04/09/fight-us-not-one-of-us/> Accessed on 12/11/2019

and some women called Samirah bint Muhaykal Asadiyah and Shifabint Abdullah were assigned to markets of Madinah to supervise and ensure the conformity to market rules. It should be noted however that, the work of the above ladies officially might have been directed towards the female merchants and customers, since the names of many females merchants like Asma bint Muharribah, Hawlat bint Suwyb, Mula'al Amariyah, can be found in the literary works of the time.³³

After the death of Prophet (SAW) the four righteous caliphs (R.T.A) carried out the functions of *muhtassib* (commanding what is good and forbidding what is bad)

When Abubakar became the first caliph, after Prophet's demise, the *ummah* was faced with apostasy. The apostasy was of three types:

1. Those who refused to give alms (Zakat)
2. Those who claimed Prophet-hood
3. Those who denounced faith.³⁴

Thus, those that used to give Prophet alms refused to give, while people such as Musailamatul Kaddhab Aswadul Ansi claimed Prophethood and many Arabs denounced their faith and reverted to idol worship. The three problems listed above, faced by the Abubakar Al-Sadiq (R.A) and were properly dealt with. He was firm on taking strong and prompt actions so that others may take heed.

Caliph ʿUmar Ibn Khattāb (R.A) was like any other caliph. He commanded what is right and forbade what is wrong. When he became the second caliph he took care of market imperfections, distortions and malpractices. Whenever Umar (R.A) went out for investigations, he used to carry a whip for striking anyone who deserves it; he also used to clear congested roads, crowded by merchants to create no hurdles. At an instance he destroyed a blacksmith's bellows because it narrowed the road where it

³³ S. D Dogan Daji (2000) 'The Institution of *Hisbah* During Islamic Classical Period Precedence of the Holy Prophet and the Four Rightly Guided Caliphs' IIT Journal of Islamization of Knowledge and Contemporary Issues Vol. 5 No. 1, p.86

³⁴ Ibid

was placed. A comparable case was his action on noticing and punishing a man who had diluted milk with water.³⁵

Uthmān Ibn Affan (R.A) was also like other caliphs, he also enjoined the right and forbade the wrong. It was narrated from Ubaidullah that people were talking too much about Al-walid (caliph Usman's brother) for his too much consuming of alcohol, when Ubaidullah talked to Usman, Usman promised to deal with him, Usman ordered Ali Ibn Abi Talib to flog him, Ali flogged him (Al-walid) eighty lashes

Caliph Ali Ibn Abi Talib (R.A) commanded what is right and forbade what is wrong (*Hisbah*), right from the time of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) Imam Muslim reported that:

“Ali Ibn Abi Talib said to me, would I not send you on the same principles as the messenger of Allah (blessing and peace be upon him) had sent me? Do not leave statues; but that you should destroy idols and you should level the high graves.”

It can be deduced from the above *Hadith* that Ali Ibn Talib (R.A) had commanded what is right and forbade what is wrong (*Hisbah*) right from the time of Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

From the forgoing therefore, it is submitted that the institution of *hisbah* which was eventually sustained by the Muslim leaders is traceable to the era of the Prophet although the name *hisbah* has not been so given by scholars.

9. ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES IN NIGERIA AND ISLAMIC LAW

The Nigerian market world is familiar with ample economic malpractices. Some of these malpractices have been given techno-legal discussions by jurists as well as Islamic legal authors. The features of Islamic business entail honesty in business practices by ensuring adherence to correct measurement and full weight. The author added that it is not expected of someone to vilify others' business so that people can buy from him and above all, every temptation to engage in hoarding must be resisted. Be that as it may, the following economic malpractices as explained by Islamic law experts are ubiquitous in Nigerian markets and marketers:

³⁵ Available on <https://www.shiachat.com/forum/topic/235036535-mixing-water-with-milk-prohibited-by-umar/> Accessed on 13/11/2019

1. *At-Tas'ir* (price fixing): this is a popular phenomenon in Nigeria markets. Prior to the advent of Islam, rich traders fixed prices of commodities in order to make large profit³⁶ and this undoubtedly brought untold hardship to the potential consumers as the prices of goods and services were excessively high. It must be noted however that Islamic law protects rights of the merchants and those of the consumers and by implication, merchants are ordinarily allowed to fix the prices of their goods and services provided that it will be reasonably fixed while putting into consideration the provisions of Islamic law. It was reported that Umar bn Khattab passed by Hatib bn Abi Balta'ah who had been underselling some of his raisings in the market. Umar said to him 'increase the price or leave our market'.³⁷ It is discernible therefore that where price fixing is not put to a check and regulation, the smaller merchants with low resources and goods will be at the mercy of the well-established merchants. Similarly, the consumers may be at the receiving end. It is observed therefore, that in Nigerian markets, underselling is an uncommon unethical economic malpractice. It has always been price hike in order to gain excessive profit through the exploitation of choiceless consumers. In essence, price fixing maybe underselling or price ceiling. The former is approved in the Hanbali and Shafi'i schools of legal thought to the effect that traders or merchants are allowed to sell their goods below market price. They premised their argument on the Hadith of Prophet where he said 'Leave people to receive the bounty of Allah from among them'³⁸. However, the Maliki and Hanafi Schools hold a contrary opinion. They argued that Umar once stopped a trader from selling below market price³⁹. The latter being price ceiling is between open market and price fixing. The advocates of price fixing argued that it is in the interest of the public not to sell above market price and abuse the consumers⁴⁰. This is not to stop them from making profit but to prevent excessive exploitation of the consumers. The proponents of open-market argued that forcing people to sell their goods at a fixed price

³⁶ Abdullah Alwi Haji Hassan (1994) 'Sales and Contracts in Early Islamic Commercial Law' (Islamabad: Islamic Research Institute) p.32

³⁷ Abdullah Alwi Haji Hassan...p.33

³⁸ Cited in Al-Shawkani *NailulAl-Awfar* (Vol. v., Matba'ah Al-Uthmaniyah Al-Masriyah, nd) p.164

³⁹ Razali H.J *Islamic Law on Commercial Transactions* (CERT, Kuala Lumpur 2009) p.33

⁴⁰ Razali...p.36

without legal justification is a form of injustice and it is unlawful⁴¹. They cited the hadith below:

When the prices of goods have increased, the people came to the Messenger of Allah and said to him: O Messenger of Allah, control the price for us! The Prophet said: Allah is the Controller of prices, the Taker and Disposer and I hope that when I meet Him, none of you will claim against me for having committed injustice to him in blood and property⁴²

Otherwise known as economic sharp practice, Islamic law prohibits every act of economic malpractice. From example, in the Qur'an, Allah says:

Woes to those who give less

When they take measure from people, they take it in full

But if y give by measure, they give less⁴³

2. *Al-Ihtikar* (Hoarding): this is the storing of foodstuff or holding them in expectation of a rise in their prices. Ordinarily, goods or foodstuff can be hoarded to provide surplusage as immediate response to scarcity. But where it is hoarded to create artificial scarcity and price hike, it becomes illegal. It was reported that Umar once said 'do not sell in our markets as a hoarder'⁴⁴
3. Outbidding (*Al-Musawamah*): this is where a consumer offers a higher price to what has been previously offered by another. It is unlawful for a consumer to make such offer and also for the seller. The prophet was reported to have said 'Do not let any of you bid against each other'⁴⁵.

10. ADDRESSING ECONOMIC MALPRACTICES IN NIGERIA THROUGH THE INSTITUTION OF HISBAH

Where a society is largely influenced by pristine Islamic rules, ethics and values, the institution of hisbah certainly occupies a premium place in governance and interpersonal relationship, economic activities inclusive. The role of Hisbah is

⁴¹ Razali...p.36

⁴² Imam Malik, *Al-Muwatta* p.297

⁴³ *Al-Mutaffifin* verses 1-3

⁴⁴ Abdullah Alwi Haji Hassan...p.35

⁴⁵ Abdullah Alwi Haji Hassan...p.37

significant to ensure the application of Shari'ah by the public in social and business transactions⁴⁶. Globally, the practice of hisbah has evolved as a major tool in administering every sphere of the society. Just as other governance theories, the institution of hisbah is not without opposition. Chief among the concerns of the opponents of hisbah is its tendency to occasion violation and abuse of human rights. But no doubt, hisbah is a veritable tool of safeguarding moral values and upholding social justice.

Hisbah is one of the earliest economic institutions in Islam. The precedent was set by the Prophet (PBUH) himself, who used to inspect markets and give instructions for just and fair dealings. His rightly guided successors followed the practice and generally performed their governmental assignments using his styles⁴⁷. In essence, Islam addresses every sphere of human concerns. It addresses *Ibadat* (worship) and *Mu'amalah* (interpersonal relationship) one of whose domains is trading or doing business and indeed Islam brings ethical dimension and morality values in business⁴⁸

Suffices to say that a number of European States have adopted the institution of Hisbah. For example, when European powers which came to the Middle East for crusade occupied Jerusalem in the 11th and 12th centuries, they decided to retain Hisbah system and allowed Hisbah officers to check markets and shops, to prevent poor goods to be brought by vendors and peddled to the market, and make sure that basic necessities such as bread and oil are always available in the market⁴⁹. Contrary to the fear of impeding free enterprise and commercial freedom, hisbah's role in managing economic malpractices within Nigerian markets and marketers cannot be overemphasized. Of popular economic sharp practice in Nigeria is seasonal artificial scarcity and price hike⁵⁰. With the institution of hisbah as it is done in some parts of the country, the institution can complement several abortive and inadequate

⁴⁶ Dogarawa 'Hisbah and the Promotion of Ethical Business Practice: A Reflection for the Shariah Implementing States in Nigeria' (International Journal of Islamic and Middle Eastern Finance and Management 2013) available at <https://doi.org/10.1108/17538391311310743> accessed 12 March, 2024

⁴⁷ Abdulazeem Islahi 'Works on Market Supervision and Shari'ah Governance by the Sixteenth Century Scholars' available at

⁴⁸ Zafar, M and Sulaiman, A 'CSR Narrative under Islamic Banking Paradigm' (Social Responsibility Journal, 2019) <https://doi.org/10.1108/SRJ-09-2018-0230>

⁴⁹ H. Ates 'A Pioneering Institution of Ombudsman: Hisbah' available at A PIONEERING INSTITUTION FOR OMBUDSMAN: HISBAH (researchgate.net) accessed on 25 April, 2024

⁵⁰ For example, the price of livestock especially ram and cow skyrockets when the Muslims are approaching Eid-el-Kabir. During December/January, prices food items and birds (especially chicken) are at the mercy of dealers and at the detriments of potential consumers.

governmental efforts⁵¹ in addressing economic malpractices. In managing commercial sharp practices, Khan argues that prohibition of all evils and misdemeanors lying and dishonesty which include ensuring no dishonesty with regards to weights and manufactured goods⁵². He added that keeping a check on the practice of hoarding and checking business fraud and adopt policy for its eradication are expected of Hisbah.

The institution of Hisbah offers large opportunities to address many socio-economic challenges, management of economic malpractices inclusive. In some states of Nigeria, the institution of Hisbah has legal status⁵³ and to an appreciable degree, the states have recorded tumultuous breakthroughs in managing socio-economic malaises. If the potentials of Hisbah is fully unleashed, it can address economic malpractices in Nigeria through a number of channels such as monitoring of prices of commodities, quality control of goods and services, supervision of scales and measurement of goods, periodic sensitization of people on the danger of engaging in economic malpractices and lastly, oversight function or supervision of Nigerian markets and marketers towards ensuring maximum compliance with the extant and pristine Islamic code for economic activities.

11. LITERATURE REVIEW

A few works on the discourse at hand are reviewed hereunder.

Ma' Rijal Al-Hisbah: Tawjihaat wa Fatawa⁵⁴ dissects the epistemology of hisbah. He asserts that hisbah entails encouraging what is good while forbidding what is bad. The author mentions some ethics and etiquettes of hisbah corp; a person inviting people to good and refraining people from doing bad. He contends that one needs not be appointed an officer of hisbah or hisbah corps before he can encourage people to do good and discourage them from doing bad.

⁵¹ For example, the enactment of Price Control Act of 2004, the establishment of Petroleum Product Pricing Regulatory Commission in 2003, Federal Competition and Consumer Protection Commission established in 2020, Standard Organization of Nigeria established in 2015 etc

⁵² M.A Khan 'The role of Islamic State in Consumer Protection' (Pakistan Journal of Islamic Research, 2008) Vol.8

⁵³ For example, the respective Houses of Assembly Kano, Zamfara, Sokoto and Kebbi States have passed laws creating Hisbah in those states.

⁵⁴ Uthaymeen M.S, *Ma Rijal Al-Hisbah Tawjihaat Wa Fatawah* (Matba'ah Sa'eer, Riyadh: Saudi Arabia 1431AH)

‘The Role of Hisbah in Promoting Ethical Values among the Muslim Ummah in the Classical Period of Islām’⁵⁵ traces the morphological root of Hisbah. It gives the definition of Hisbah to mean enjoining what is good and forbidding what is bad. The article argues that Hisbah is traceable to the era of the Prophet and was upheld by the four successive caliphs. It mentions the areas affected by Hisbah in these eras. Summarily, what Hisbah was during the caliphate of Umayyad was enunciated.

Anwar’s work⁵⁶ principally studied the institution of hisbah as it concerns business ethics. The author mentioned that Islam approves trading with a view to making profit but much must be done within the ambit of Islamic law. Price control, quality control, control of scale and measurement are discussed while emphasizing the place of hisbah in ensuring maximum compliance with the provision of Islamic law. The paper concludes that understanding of Islamic business ethics is diverse hence the need of hisbah in place to ensure people understand business ethics as enshrined in Islamic law. Wonokromo, a traditional market in Malaysia is used as a case study in his work.

12. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

The study finds that:

1. Economic malpractices exist in Nigeria.
2. Through various enactments in Nigeria, there are a number of regulatory bodies whose primary duty is to prevent all forms of economic indecencies but same are inadequate and inefficient in addressing economic malpractices.
3. It is imperative to borrow Hisbah as a veritable institution in furtherance of complementing the existing measures put in place in Nigeria to address economic improprieties.

⁵⁵ Tambari A.B&Ahmad M.D ‘The Role of Hisbah in Promoting Ethical Values among the Muslim Ummah in the Classical Period of Islam’ 2018 Journal of Islamic Studies and Culture vol. 6 no.2

⁵⁶ Anwar M.K, ‘The Role of Al-Hisbah in Implementation of Business Ethics in Traditional Markets’ https://www.bing.com/search?q=The+Role+of+Al-Hisbah+in+Implementation+of+Business+Ethics+in+Traditional+Markets&cv=81baf3e4d7849a0a69540odd5d48540&gs_lcrp=EgZjaHJvbWUyBggAEEUYOTIGCAEQRRhAogEIMTQ2N2owajmoAgCwAgA&FORM=ANAB01&PC=U531 accessed on November 10, 2023.

13. Conclusion

Thus far, this paper has given the techno-legal and conceptual meanings of *hisbah* as well as the legal basis of *hisbah* in Islamic law. In addition, it discussed the concept of economic malpractices as operative in Nigeria. It was discovered that despite the establishment of several bodies through various Acts to curb economic malpractices, it was discovered that same are inadequate and inefficient. But in Nigeria, a number of states with *hisbah* in place through a number of methods have been able to address a number of socio-economic challenges in Nigeria. With the institution of *Hisbah* embraced, it will guarantee an effective and efficient mechanism of curbing the exploitative tendency cum economic malpractices of Nigerian marketers and markets.